

Preparation and Characterisation of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Transition Elements. Part II. Complexes of Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)

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A number of metal complexes of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{phth})\text{am}_x\text{ or dam}_x]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{phth})\text{am}_x\text{ or dam}_x]$ where, phth, am and dam stand for phthalate ion, an aromatic or heterocyclic amine and a diamine respectively, have been isolated by treating metal(II) phthalate with the required amount of the ligand in absolute ethanol. The formulae of complexes have been confirmed by the elemental analysis, conductivity and molecular weight studies. The magnetic and spectral measurements have also been done and these show that the nickel(II) complexes are hexaco-ordinated with octahedral geometries, while the cobalt(II) complexes of aromatic or heterocyclic amines possess tetrahedral and those of diamines, octahedral configurations. The assignment of absorption bands has been made and the value of ligand field parameters are calculated.

THE survey of reported literature shows that a very large number of complexes of first row transition elements with many inorganic anions, have been studied. The organic anions have not been given much attention, although some complexes of organic anionic salts of the metals have been reported from this laboratory¹. The phthalate ion is a bulky organic anion possessing two COO^- groups which show strong tendency to co-ordinate with the metals, besides neutralising its charge. In the previous communication, studies on the amine complexes of copper(II) phthalate were reported¹. The present paper records the preparation and characterisation of some ten complexes of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) phthalates with ammonia, pyridine, *p*-toluidine and some diamines like ethylene or propylenediamine and 2-2' dipyridyl. The measurements of their conductivity, molecular weight, infra-red, magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra have been made and the results have been interpreted in a consistent manner.

Experimental

Preparation of Complexes :—The complexes were prepared by treating a suspension of the appropriate metal(II) phthalate in absolute ethanol with a large excess of the corresponding amine and refluxing the solution for ten hours. The reaction mixture was concentrated by distilling off excess of solvent and the complex was crystallised on cooling. The results of the elemental analysis are given in Table 1.

Molecular Weight and Conductance :—The conductances were measured in nitrobenzene at a concentration of 10^{-3} M on a Philips PR 9500/90 magic

eye type instrument and molecular weights were also determined in nitrobenzene cryoscopically and the values are given in Table 1.

Magnetic Susceptibilities, Infra-red and Electronic Spectra :—Magnetic measurements were made on powdered sample by the Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant and the μ_{eff} values are given in Tables 2 and 3. The infra-red spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 spectrometer in the region $4000\text{-}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while the electronic spectra were obtained on a Cary 14 recording instrument in the range $200\text{-}2000\text{ nm}$ and absorption maxima listed in Tables 2 and 3.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis show the molecular formulae to be $[\text{Ni}(\text{am})_4\text{ or }(\text{dam})_2\text{ phth}]$, where am stands for ammonia or pyridine and dam for ethylene or propylene diamine and 2-2' dipyridyl; $[\text{Co}(\text{am})_2\text{ phth}]$ where am=pyridine or *p*-toluidine and $[\text{Co}(\text{dam})_2\text{ phth}]$ where dam=ethylene or propylene diamine and 2-2' dipyridyl. The values of molar conductances and molecular weights suggest that complexes are non-electrolytes, thereby showing that the phthalate ion is co-ordinated to the metal. The nickel(II) complexes are thus hexa co-ordinated, while the cobalt(II) complexes of pyridine and *p*-toluidine are tetra and those of di-amines hexa co-ordinated.

The co-ordination of amine to metal is indicated by the shifts in the relevant infra-red band frequencies. The assignment of the bands has been made by analogy to the other reported complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA

Compound No.	Formula	%M	%C	%H	%N	Mol. wt.	Molar conductance mhos.
1.	[Ni(NH ₃) ₄ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	19.80 (20.21)*	32.65 (33.04)	5.72 (5.50)	19.65 (19.02)	270.5 (290.78)	0.526
2.	[Ni(C ₈ H ₈ N) ₄ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	10.25 (10.89)	62.90 (62.39)	4.10 (4.26)	10.26 (10.89)	—	—
3.	[Ni(C ₈ H ₈ N ₂) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄] .2H ₂ O	16.05 (15.49)	38.50 (38.04)	6.72 (6.33)	14.95 (14.78)	330.8 (378.8)	0.628
4.	[Ni(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄] .2H ₂ O	14.12 (14.42)	41.66 (41.08)	6.72 (6.90)	13.90 (13.75)	382.5 (406.84)	0.418
5.	[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	10.60 (10.95)	63.15 (62.85)	3.42 (3.55)	10.95 (10.46)	—	—
6.	[Co(p-C ₇ H ₇ N) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄] .2H ₂ O	12.90 (12.30)	55.46 (55.84)	5.28 (5.49)	5.61 (5.91)	437.40 (473.13)	0.625
7.	[Co(C ₈ H ₈ N) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	15.30 (15.45)	54.62 (54.14)	3.75 (3.67)	7.85 (7.32)	345.3 (381.08)	0.360
8.	[Co(C ₈ H ₈ N ₂) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄] .2H ₂ O	15.21 (15.53)	38.25 (38.89)	6.52 (6.43)	15.60 (15.30)	354.6 (379.02)	—
9.	[Co(C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄] .2H ₂ O	14.85 (14.46)	41.20 (41.06)	6.85 (6.91)	13.21 (13.75)	—	0.625
10.	[Co(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂) ₂ C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	11.55 (11.05)	61.20 (61.86)	3.92 (3.71)	10.60 (10.45)	495.0 (535.18)	—

* Values in parentheses refer to calculated ones.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC DATA OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES

Complex No.	μ_{eff} B.M.	V_1 in kK	V_2 in kK	Mean value V_2 in kK	V_3 in kK	V_3/V_1	Dq in cm ⁻¹	B in cm ⁻¹	β^-
1.	3.0	9.09	15.62 14.28	14.95	25.04	1.64	909	927	0.85
2.	3.4	9.01	14.92	—	25.32	1.66	900	919	0.85
3.	3.0	9.90	17.69 16.00	16.84	27.78	1.70	990	1062	0.18
4.	3.0	9.80	17.54 15.87	16.71	27.78	1.70	980	1000	0.92
5.	3.4	9.74	17.85 16.13	16.99	28.57	1.65	974	994	0.91

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC DATA OF COBALT(II) COMPLEXES

Complex No.	μ_{eff} B.M.	V_1 in kK	V_2 in kK	V_3 in kK	Mean value V_3 in kK	Dq in cm ⁻¹	B in cm ⁻¹	β^-
6.	4.5	6.21	16.13	29.41	—	345	786	0.70
7.	4.6	6.17	15.87	20.07	—	343	781	0.70
8.	5.0	7.64	16.18	20.83 19.59	20.21	970	932	0.83
9.	5.4	7.66	16.13	20.83 19.23	20.03	973	934	0.83
10.	5.3	7.69	16.26	20.83 18.87	19.85	977	988	0.83

The co-ordination of

(I) ammonia and *p*-toluidine is indicated by the negative shifts of NH stretching frequency, which is observed in complexes around 3300 cm⁻¹;

(II) pyridine is shown by the shifts of the group of five bands between 990-1031 cm⁻¹ and the 8a band of the free ligand at 1538 cm⁻¹ to higher wave number²⁻⁴;

(III) ethylene or propylene diamine can be inferred by the negative shift of NH stretching frequency of the order of 100-200 cm⁻¹;

(IV) 2, 2' dipyridyl to the two metal ions is indicated by the shift of 1576, 1137, 1087 and 400 cm⁻¹ bands of free ligand to higher wave numbers^{5,6}, and

(V) phthalate ion has been correlated with the presence of the asymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ stretching frequencies at 1700 and 1430 cm⁻¹ respectively characteristic of co-ordinated carboxylation⁷.

The i. r. results thus confirm the co-ordination of amines as well as the phthalate ions to the metal.

The geometries of the complexes have been assigned by the magnetic and spectral data as follows :

The μ_{eff} values of all the nickel(II) complexes is in the range 3.00-3.40 B. M. indicating high spin hexa co-ordinated structures, which are confirmed electronic spectra, where the three characteristic transitions of the octahedral configuration V_1 , V_2 and V_3 are seen around 9.09, 14.95 and 25.61 $\text{kK}^{8,9}$. The V_2 transition is in fact broken down in two components in consequence of the lowering of the symmetry from truly octahedral to distorted octahedral due to the presence of a mixed ligand field around the metal.

The cobalt(II) phthalate complexes of pyridine and *p*-toluidine are also high spin and the μ_{eff} is around 4.66 B. M. This along with electronic spectral data confirm tetrahedral structures.

The diamine complexes of cobalt(II) phthalate are hexa co-ordinated octahedral and consequently possess higher value of μ_{eff} between 5.00 – 5.30 B.M. and show the V_1 , V_2 and V_3 bands of octahedral structure at 7.65, 16.20 and 20.83 kK^{10-13} .

The V_1 and V_2 are observed as single component but V_3 band shows two components, one at 480 and the other at 502 nm and as mentioned in previous paragraph its splitting is a consequence of the lowering of octahedral symmetry due to presence of a mixed ligand field around the metal.

The values of $10 Dq$ and B have been calculated by equations outlined by Figgis¹⁴ and are listed in Tables 2 and 3. It should, however, be pointed out that in such mixed ligand complexes as being reported here, the values of these parameters is only approximate due to the observational inaccuracies in determining band centers and therefore should be used only for comparative purposes. It thus appears

that the ligand field which in the present case is derived from some M–O and some M–N bonds, is weaker in nature than the ligand field derived from allequivalent M–O or M–N bonds. However, these values are accurate enough to assign tetrahedral or distorted octahedral structures to the complexes.

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